

Population and Economic Growth: a Panel Causality Analysis

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Abstract

This paper examines the relationship between population growth and economic growth using panel data from 111 countries over the period from 1960 to 2019. In the first stage of the analysis, we divided the sample into three groups of countries using a non-parametric method. Unlike the ad hoc decisions made in previous studies, which were based on factors such as size or economic performance, these categories were determined objectively. We conducted a Granger causality analysis on internally homogeneous groups, composed of countries with similar trajectories in population and economic growth, which are clearly distinct from one another. Our results reveal significant qualitative differences in the dynamics of population and economic growth between these groups.

Keywords

time series analysis; minimal spanning tree; hierarchical tree; population dynamics; economic growth; panel causality test

JEL codes: C10; C14; C38; J10; O40

Introduction

According to the last United Nations¹ the global population has surpassed 8 billion. Projections indicate a trend of slowing growth followed by stabilization. However, this pattern is not uniform across all countries, with some experiencing zero population

1 United Nations Department of Economic and Social Affairs, Population Division (2022). *World Population Prospects 2022: Summary of Results*. UN DESA/POP/2022/TR/NO. 3.

growth rates while others are expected to maintain high rates in the coming years. Even if these projections prove accurate, there is no indication that migratory movements will cease, implying that the composition and size of populations will continue to change in both origin and destination countries. As long as modern economies do not achieve stable population levels in terms of size and composition, they will inevitably face continuous repercussions on economic growth, which, in turn, directly affects overall societal welfare. Fluctuations in population growth rates can influence both supply and demand dynamics, while economic growth itself can shape population growth patterns. However, the specific scope and mechanisms through which these interdependencies manifest across diverse economies remain uncertain. This paper contributes to the existing empirical literature on the complex relationship between economic and population growth.

The ties between population and economic growth have long been a subject of debate among economists, demographers, and policymakers. The core of this discussion centers on the potential effects of both rapid and slow population growth on economic performance and societal well-being. Despite extensive historical discourse, there is still no theoretical consensus on the mechanisms, channels, causes, and effects that underpin the relationship between these two variables. While a wealth of empirical literature addresses the issue, it has done little to resolve the debate, and reaching a unanimous conclusion remains challenging.

Population acts both as a driver and a beneficiary of economic growth. A significant portion of the population constitutes the workforce, one of the key factors behind economic development. At the same time, the ultimate objective of growth is to improve the overall welfare of the population. Understanding the relationship between these two dynamics is crucial for comprehending the broader phenomenon of growth. However, there is still no agreement on whether population growth is beneficial, neutral, or detrimental to economic growth. Similarly, there is also no consensus on how economic growth affects population dynamics – though this direction of causation has received far less attention in the literature.

Modern growth theories approach population differently than classical models. Standard growth models typically treat population as an exogenous variable, assuming it grows at a fixed rate. Solow's model (Solow 1956) predicts a negative relationship between population growth and per capita income. In the long run, a higher population growth rate is associated with lower steady-state per capita output. In the short run, a higher population growth rate leads to slower per capita output growth during the transition to the new steady-state equilibrium.

The model does not distinguish between population and the labor force, implicitly assuming that both grow at the same rate or in a stable manner. In this framework, the assumption of decreasing marginal returns results in stable or fixed per capita output. According to the model, sustained growth can only be achieved through continuous technological progress.

In contrast, some endogenous growth models (Romer 1986, Romer 1990) suggest a positive relationship between population and economic growth. In these models, population is not merely a proxy for the labor force but also represents the source of scientists and innovators. The larger the population, the more technological progress is expected. Moreover, a larger population generates higher demand for innovative goods, altering human capital endowments and leading to greater productivity (Kuznets 1967; Kremer 1993; Simon 1989).

This approach deviates from earlier growth models by introducing controversial scale effects.

Other theoretical approaches adopt the classic method of treating population as an endogenously determined variable. Hansen and Prescott (2002), Irmen (2004), Musa (2015), Corchón (2016), and more recently, Bucci et al. (2019), among others, have developed models in which the relationship between population growth and economic growth is non-monotonic, exhibiting effects that vary in magnitude, direction, and sign.

In summary, several channels have been identified through which rapid population growth could negatively affect economic growth. These include reducing savings rates and the capital-labor ratio (dilution effect), increasing the dependency ratio, and placing pressure on health, education, and social protection systems, as well as causing environmental strain. At the same time, potential positive effects are recognized: a growing population stimulates demand, enables economies of scale, and serves as a source of innovation.

This paper is organized as follows. The next section provides a brief review of the empirical literature on the relationship between economic growth and demographic change. The subsequent sections present the data and describe the clustering methodology used to group countries into homogeneous categories, followed by the panel causality test applied in the study. We then present the empirical results, with the final section offering concluding remarks.

A Brief Review of Empirical Literature

On the empirical side, Granger causality and cointegration analysis (Granger 1969; Engle and Granger 1987), along with the Maddison Project's Penn tables – especially Maddison (1995) – have significantly advanced comparative analyses of the interaction between population and economic growth. In empirical studies examining the relationship between economic growth and demographic change, there is a strong focus on testing for cointegration between the two variables and exploring their causal relationships.

To contextualize our research, we provide a brief review of the relevant empirical literature, summarized in Table 1. This review covers studies that investigate the causality between population and economic growth, including those that consider population growth as one of the determinants of economic growth. However, we do not include studies that examine closely related aspects, such as the impact of aging on economic growth (Verdiyeva 2019; Maestas et al. 2023). While not exhaustive, this review offers a sufficiently broad overview to represent the empirical studies on this topic conducted over the past forty years.

Table 1. Summary of Empirical Literature Reviewed

Author	Period	Sample	Estimation Method	Findings
Jung and Qudus 1986	1950-1980	44 countries	Granger Causality test	$p \rightarrow +y$ $p \rightarrow -y$ $y \rightarrow +p$ $y \rightarrow -p$ Non Causality

Author	Period	Sample	Estimation Method	Findings
Kapuria-Foreman 1995	1961-1991	Nepal	Granger Causality test	$p \rightarrow + y$
	1961-1990	India		$p + \leftrightarrow - ** y$
	1953-1989	China		$p - \leftrightarrow + ** y$
	1951-1990	Ghana		$y \leftrightarrow - p$
	1953-1989	Sri Lanka		$y \leftrightarrow - p$
	1961-1991	Bolivia		Non Causality
	1949-1991	Philippines		Non Causality
	1952-1991	Guatemala		$p \rightarrow + ** y$
	1961-1990	Syria		$y \rightarrow - p$
	1961-1990	Peru		$y \rightarrow - * p$
	1951-1990	Thailand		Non Causality
	1958-1990	Turkey		$p - \leftrightarrow + ** y$
	1961-1990	Chile		$p - \leftrightarrow + ** y$
	1952-1990	Argentina		Non Causality
	1948-1986	Mexico		$p \rightarrow + ** y$
Nakibulla 1998	1960-1990	Bangladesh	VAR	$y \rightarrow + p$
Dawson and Tiffin 1998	1950-1993	India	Cointegration (Johansen)	Non Causality
Darrat and Al-Yousif 1999	1950-1996	20 countries	Cointegration, VEC	$p \rightarrow + * y$
Thornton 2001	1900–1994	Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Venezuela	Granger Causality Test, VAR	Non Causality
	1925-1994	Colombia		
	1921-1994	Mexico		
	1913-1994	Peru		
Tsen and Fu-ruoka 2005	1950-2000	Japan, Korea, Thailand	Cointegration (Johansen), VAR	$p \leftrightarrow y$
		China, Singapore, Philippines		$p \rightarrow y$
		Hong Kong, Malaysia		$y \rightarrow p$
		Taiwan, Indonesia		Non Causality
An and Jeon 2006	1960-2000	25 OCDE countries	cross-country regression non-parametric kernel	Inverted relation U-shape
Faria et al. 2006	1950-2000	125 countries	OLS $(\log y), (\log y)^2$	Africa – Asia: U-shape inverted; Europe: $y \rightarrow - p$
Yao et al. 2007	1954-2005	Taiwan	Cointegration (Johansen), VAR, Toda-Yamamoto	until 2000 $p \rightarrow + y$; until 2005 insignificant

Author	Period	Sample	Estimation Method	Findings
Azomahou and Mishra 2008	1960-2000	110 countries	GAM, Non-parametric	nonlinear effect
Afsal 2009	1950-2001	Pakistan	OLS	Negative effect ($p \rightarrow y$)
Choudhry and Elhorst 2010	1961-2003	China, India, Pakistan	OLS	Positive effect (growth differential pop of working age – total pop): 46% (China), 39% (India), 25% (Pakistan)
Mulok et al. 2011	1960-2009	Malaysia	Cointegration (Johansen), VAR, Toda-Yamamoto	Non Causality
Yao et al. 2013	1952-2007	China	Co-integration, VECM	$p \rightarrow -y$
Liu and Hu 2013	1983-2008	Chinese provinces (panel)	OLS	$p \rightarrow -y$
Huang and Xie 2013	1980-2007	Panel 90 countries	simultaneous ADL	$p \rightarrow -y$
Song 2013	1965-2009	13 Asian countries	OLS	Negative effect $p \rightarrow y$
Ali et al. 2013	1975-2008	Pakistan	ARDL	$p \rightarrow +y$
Furuoka 2013	1960-2007	Indonesia	Cointegration (Johansen)	$p \rightarrow +y$
Chang et al. 2017	1870-2013	Finland, France, Portugal, Sweden Canada, Germany, Japan, Norway, Switzerland Austria, Italy Belgium, Denmark, Netherlands, UK, US, New Zealand	Panel Granger Causality Test	$p \rightarrow +y$ $y \rightarrow -p$ $p \leftrightarrow y$ Non Causality
Musa 2015	1980-2013	India	Cointegration (Johansen), VEC	$p \rightarrow +^*y$
Garza-Rodriguez et al. 2016	1962-2012	Mexico	VEC	$p \leftrightarrow y$
Sibe et al. 2016	1960-2013	30 of the most Populated Countries	VEC	$p \leftrightarrow y$
Rahman et al. 2017	1960-2013	USA, UK, Canada, China, India, Brazil	Panel Cointegration, VEC	$p \rightarrow +y$

Author	Period	Sample	Estimation Method	Findings
Alvarez-Diaz et al. 2018	1960 – 2010	28 states of the European Union	ARDL	$p \leftrightarrow y$
Furuoka 2018	1961-2014	China	ARDL	$p \leftrightarrow y$
Aksoy et al. 2019	1970-2014	21 OECD countries	Panel VAR	$p \rightarrow + y$
Mahmoudinia 2020	1980-2018	57 Islamic countries	Cointegration (Johansen), VEC	$p \rightarrow + y$
Sebikabu et al. 2020	1974-2013	Rwanda	ARDL	$p \rightarrow + y$

Notes: the table summarizes the results found in the literature review. In the ‘Results’ column, ‘ $y \rightarrow p$ ’ indicates a unidirectional causal relationship (Granger causality) where per capita income Granger causes population. ‘ $p \rightarrow y$ ’ indicates that population Granger causes per capita income. ‘ $p \leftrightarrow y$ ’ indicates a bidirectional causal relationship. The symbols ‘+’ or ‘-’ and ‘*’ indicate the sign and significance, respectively, when reported.

Empirical research on the links between economic growth and population growth has not produced conclusive results, and significant variations are observed across studies. In terms of causal relationships, particularly within the Granger causality framework, a wide range of outcomes emerges:

a) $p \rightarrow y$, unidirectional causality, population growth stimulates economic growth: Darrat and Al-Yousif (1999), Yao et al. (2007), Liu and Hu (2013), Ali et al. (2013), Furuoka (2013), Musa (2015), Sebikabu et al. (2020).

b) $y \rightarrow p$, unidirectional causality, economic growth stimulates population growth: Nakibulla (1998).

c) $p \leftrightarrow y$, bidirectional causality, population growth stimulates and is stimulated by economic growth: Garza-Rodriguez et al. (2016), Alvarez-Diaz et al. (2018), Furuoka (2018).

d) non causality, population growth neither stimulates nor is stimulated by economic growth: Dawson and Tiffin (1998), Thornton (2001), Mulok (2011).

e) mixed results: Jung and Quddus (1986), Kapuria-Foreman (1995), Tsen and Furuoka (2005), Chang et al. (2017).

It should be noted that the majority of the surveyed studies focus on analyzing specific countries or groups of countries individually, with a particular emphasis on highly populated developing nations. The limited number of studies that use a panel approach tend to rely on ad hoc criteria, such as population size (Sibe et al. 2016; Rahman et al. 2017), membership in an economic bloc (Alvarez-Diaz et al. 2018; Aksoy et al. 2019), or cultural attributes (Mahmoudinia 2020). The criteria used to categorize each group may affect the results.

In this article, the first stage of our analysis introduces a non-parametric technique that allows us to compare the dynamics of demographic and economic growth across a large sample of countries. This method generates homogeneous groups using a statistical criterion derived from the data itself. Once the clusters were defined, an econometric model was specified for each group within a panel data framework. This approach helped overcome one of the main limitations of standard panel data analysis, which, when applied to heterogeneous countries, may not always be suitable. In addition to incorporating temporal information, this method also accounted for cross-sectional dependency.

Data and methodology

Data

Throughout this research, the dynamics of population and economic growth are represented by the population growth rate and per capita GDP growth rate, respectively. Annual data on per capita GDP (in 2011 constant dollars, PPP-adjusted) and population, along with their respective growth rates, were obtained from the Penn World Table 10.0 database (Feenstra et al. 2015)². This database is widely regarded as a standard source for comparative economic growth studies. It includes annual data for 111 countries over the period 1960–2019³. During this period, the aggregate world population exhibited a clear trend.

Figure 1. Population growth rate: average annual rate for 111 sample countries. *Source:* own calculations based on PWT 10.0

Figure 2. Average per capita GDP growth for 111 sample countries. *Source:* own calculations based on PTW 10.0

² Available for download at <https://www.rug.nl/ggdc/productivity/pwt/> (access date: July 2023).

³ Since our analysis requires a balanced panel, we opted to consider all countries that did not have missing data after 1960.

As shown in Figure 1, the global population growth rate has been steadily declining, following a gradual and consistent trajectory with minimal fluctuations. This pattern aligns with the well-known stages of the demographic transition. However, significant disparities exist among countries regarding the timing and pace of their demographic transitions, which is the focus of this study.

The average growth rates of population and per capita GDP (Figure 2) over the analysis period are nearly identical, at 1.8% and 1.84%, respectively. However, the similarities end there. Average per capita GDP growth lacks a clear trend and has a standard deviation eight times larger than that of population growth. Furthermore, it exhibits erratic and volatile short-term behavior, with an average annual variation 40 times larger than that of population growth.

Methodology

In this article, we propose a two-stage approach to examine the causal relationship between population growth and economic growth using panel data. In the first step, we employed a non-parametric methodology to group countries based on their homogeneous dynamics in population growth and economic development – two factors that influence the causal relationship between them. In the second stage, we tested causality by applying the procedure proposed by Dimitrescu and Hurling (2012).

Dimitrescu and Hurling (2012) extend Granger's (1969) causality test, originally designed for time series, to panel data contexts, allowing for heterogeneous effects between observational units. This enables us to test for the presence of a causal relationship between population growth and GDP growth across different country clusters.

Dimitrescu and Hurling's test relies on the cross-sectional average of individual Wald statistics associated with the standard Granger (1969) causality tests. The authors propose testing the null hypothesis of non-causality against the alternative hypothesis of causality. Under the null hypothesis, there is no causal relationship for any country in the panel. An advantage of this test is its ability to account for cross-sectional dependence, employing a block bootstrap procedure to correct empirical critical values. Accounting for this dependency is crucial, as ignoring it can lead to substantial bias and size distortions (Albaladejo et al. 2022).

To address the nature of this cause-and-effect relationship, impulse-response functions are employed to illustrate the dynamic reaction of one variable to innovations in another. These functions are estimated using a GMM panel VAR approach for the groups of countries where Granger causality is found. Our impulse response analysis assumes that the error terms are orthogonal with unit variance. Thus, a shock occurs in only one variable at a time; since the variances of the error terms are one, a unit shock is simply an innovation of size one standard deviation.

Empirical Analysis, First Step: Cluster Analysis – Identifying Countries with Similar Dynamic Behavior

To determine homogeneous groups of countries based on their dynamic patterns in population and economic growth, we employed the method suggested by Brida et al. (2020). This method involves conducting a hierarchical cluster analysis using a metric that enables the comparison of dynamic trajectories among different countries. To construct this metric,

we utilized a symbolization process that transforms the original two-dimensional series defined by the dynamic trajectories of population growth rates and GDP per capita growth rates into a symbolic series that identifies shifts in economic regimes.

To describe the qualitative behavior of the joint evolution of economic and demographic growth, we introduced the notion of a regime (Brida et al. 2003; Brida and Punzo 2003). A regime is defined as a range of conditions characterizing the behavior of a system, specifically the joint dynamics of population and per capita output. We established two conditions: one sets a threshold for yearly population change, and the other sets a threshold for yearly change in the growth rate of per capita GDP. This results in the partitioning of the state space into four regions, each corresponding to a different relationship between demographic change and economic performance – in other words, different regimes. By taking the average change in per capita income and population during the analysis period for all countries, we obtain the following partition of the state space into four regions:

$$R_1 = \{(g_p, g_y): g_p \geq \mu_p, g_y \leq \mu_y\}$$

$$R_2 = \{(g_p, g_y): g_p \geq \mu_p, g_y \geq \mu_y\}$$

$$R_3 = \{(g_p, g_y): g_p \leq \mu_p, g_y \geq \mu_y\}$$

$$R_4 = \{(g_p, g_y): g_p \leq \mu_p, g_y \leq \mu_y\}$$

If we label each regime R_i by the symbol j , we can substitute the original bi-variate time series $\{(g_{1p}, g_{1y}), (g_{2p}, g_{2y}), \dots, (g_{Tp}, g_{Ty})\}$ by a sequence of symbols $\{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_T\}$ such that $s_t = j$ if and only if (g_p, g_y) belongs to R_j . This Symbolic Series summarizes the most relevant qualitative information on the dynamics of a country's regime⁴.

When working with regime dynamics represented by symbolic sequences, we need to measure distances between symbolic sequences. Then, given two countries, i and j , with symbolic sequences $\{s_{it}\}_{t=1}^{t=T}$ and $\{s_{jt}\}_{t=1}^{t=T}$, corresponding to countries i and j , we define the following distance:

$$d(i, j) = \sqrt{\sum_{t=1}^T f(s_{it}, s_{jt})},$$

where

$$f(s_{it}, s_{jt}) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } s_{it} \neq s_{jt} \quad \forall i \neq j, \forall t. \\ 0 & \text{if } s_{it} = s_{jt} \end{cases}$$

Intuitively, the smaller the distance between two countries within the same regime, the more similarities they share. When two countries exhibit the exact same sequence of regimes, their distance is minimized to zero. The maximum possible distance is \sqrt{T} , occurring when two countries never coincide in the same regime in any given year.

After calculating all distances from the symbolic series of countries in the sample, we employed the Hierarchical Tree (HT) clustering technique to classify the countries in our study. To build this tree, we utilized the nearest neighbor single-link clustering algorithm, as described by Mantegna (1999) and Mantegna and Stanley (1999).

4 See Brida et al. (2003) and Brida and Punzo (2003) for a more detailed exposition of regime dynamics and its symbolic representation. In Brida et al. (2011) you can be found an empirical analysis on convergence clubs that apply the same approach as the one used in our paper.

In this work, we chose to build country clusters solely based on the variables central to the analysis – population and GDP. This decision is motivated by three reasons. First, the impact of other factors that differentiate countries and influence GDP or population growth is already captured indirectly through population or GDP. Second, including additional controls at this stage would compromise comparability with the causality analysis between population and GDP dynamics in the second stage. Third, graphical analysis demonstrates that each of the three country clusters is reasonably homogeneous.

Figure 3. Minimum Spanning Tree (MST). The cluster of *mature economies* is highlighted in light green, *transition economies* in yellow, and *young economies* in violet. The remaining countries exhibit trajectories that do not align with the previously identified patterns.

The MST enables the computation of the subdominant ultrametric distance matrix D^* (Rammal et al. 1986), a prerequisite for building the Hierarchical Tree (HT). Figure 4 displays the dendrogram representing the HT obtained.

Given a predetermined number of groups for dividing the sample, the Hierarchical Tree (HT) illustrates how countries should be grouped. To determine the countries in each group, the final step involves applying a hierarchical clustering stopping rule to find the optimal number of groups. Using the Calinsky stopping rule (Calinski and Harabasz 1974) results in three well-differentiated clusters, encompassing 87 out of the 111 countries (approximately 80% of the sample).

The first group, termed ‘*mature economies*,’ consists of 32 countries and is the most homogeneous among the three. It exhibits the smallest sum of group distances in the minimum

Figure 4. Hierarchical Tree of 111 countries. The three main groups. Right side (in pink): ARG, AUS, AUT, BEL, BRB, CAN, CHE, CHL, CYP, DEU, DNK, ESP, FIN, FRA, GBR, GRC, IRL, ISL, ITA, JPN, LUX, MLT, MUS, NLD, NOR, NZL, PRT, ROU, SWE, TTO, URY, USA. Middle group (in green): BRA, CHN, COL, CRI, DOM, ECU, FJI, HKG, IDN, IRN, KOR, LKA, MAR, MEX, NAN, PER, PHL, PRY, SLV, SYC, THA, TUN, TUR, TWN, VEN, ZAF. Left side group (in violet): BEN, CIV, CMR, COD, COG, COM, EGY, ETH, GHA, GIN, GMB, GTM, HND, JOR, KEN, MDG, MOZ, MRT, NER, NGA, PAK, SEN, SYR, TCD, TGO, TZA, UGA, ZMB.

spanning tree (MST). This group includes all 24 initial members of the OECD, excluding Turkey⁵. The non-OECD countries in this group (Argentina, Barbados, Malta, Mauritius, Trinidad and Tobago, Romania, and Uruguay) are currently classified as upper-income or upper-middle-income countries.

In terms of regime dynamics, the common denominator in this group is that the countries almost strictly alternate between regimes R_3 and R_4 throughout the entire analysis period. Some countries in the group, such as Canada, Chile, and Trinidad and Tobago, experience a brief initial phase alternating between R_1 and R_2 (concentrated in R_2), lasting at most for the first decade and a half of the analysis period⁶. In summary, this group comprises countries that transitioned from high to low population growth before the analysis period or, in a few cases, at the beginning of the period (before the mid-1970s).

The second group, labeled ‘*young economies*,’ comprises 28 countries and exhibits the highest level of heterogeneity among the three groups. It includes 22 Sub-Saharan African countries, three Middle Eastern countries (Egypt, Jordan, and Syria), two Central American countries (Guatemala and Honduras), and Pakistan.

⁵ By initial members, we mean the countries that joined the organization in its first decade or so of existence.

⁶ Three countries in the group, Australia, Ireland, and Luxembourg have some years alternating between R_1 and R_2 in the final 15 years of the analysis. One possible explanation: the relatively high influx of immigrants during those years. In fact, as a percentage of their population, these are the countries that received the most immigrants in the group during the last two decades.

Following the pattern observed in the previous cluster, the defining characteristic of countries in this group is that, during the analysis period, they alternate almost entirely between regimes R_1 and R_2 , mirroring the dynamics of the mature economies cluster. Among the 28 countries in this group, 16 have never visited regimes R_3 or R_4 . Mauritania, Mozambique, and Syria are exceptions, where a short phase in R_3 and R_4 can be identified. Mauritania experienced this in the 1960s, Mozambique during the 1980s, and more recently, Syria in the last decade. The anomaly in Syria is attributed to population displacement resulting from the civil war that began in 2011.

Broadly speaking, countries in the third group, labeled ‘transition economies’,⁷ exhibit two distinct phases. In the first phase, countries alternate between regimes R_1 and R_2 . In the second phase, they alternate between regimes R_3 and R_4 . The timing of transitions between these phases varies, with extreme cases such as Korea shifting to the second phase as early as the late 1970s, while the Philippines did not transition until the 2000s. There is also variation in the proportion of years with above-average economic growth within each phase. For example, during the first period, this proportion is very low for Namibia, Venezuela, and Ecuador, but very high for Taiwan and Korea. The common denominator among the 26 countries in this group is that they transition from high to low population growth during the analysis period.

Many of these countries were able to capture the demographic dividend, as indicated by the duration spent in regimes R_2 and R_3 during the analysis period.

To assess the validity of the results from this stage, we examine the evolution of one of the proximate determinants of economic growth: human capital (see Figure 5). The graphical analysis below reveals the homogeneity of each of the three country clusters. The observed deviations are primarily associated with small countries, such as Jordan (indicated by the red series reaching the upper cluster), which do not alter the central findings of the paper. The figures demonstrate minimal overlap within the range of variation of this variable and a discernible order among the groups. The predominant commonality among the three groups is their shared temporal trend. In essence, this signals the robustness of our results.

Second Step: Panel Causality Analysis

Table 2 below presents the results of the Granger causality test conducted on the country panel. The findings indicate that, considering the complete sample, a bidirectional causal relationship exists between population growth and GDP per capita growth. The p-value associated with the test statistic suggests rejecting both null hypotheses, indicating that higher population growth contributes to increased GDP growth per capita, and vice versa.

When the analysis is disaggregated by country cluster, the results remain consistent. Once again, a bidirectional causality relationship is observed between population and GDP. An exception is found among countries in Cluster 1 (*mature economies*), where higher population growth does not correspond to higher GDP growth.

The results above have interesting implications. Countries in Cluster 1 lack incentives to promote population growth, as it does not translate into higher income. In contrast, coun-

⁷ The term “transition economies” is used to refer to an economy that is undergoing a demographic transition. It is the ad hoc name we give it and is not linked to the UN or IMF classification of country types.

Figure 5. Human Capital per capita evolution per group. *Source:* PWT 10.0, Human capital index, based on years of schooling and returns to education.

Table 2. Panel causality analysis

	Complete panel	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3	Lags
H_0: population growth does not Granger-cause GDP per capita growth					
Statistic	6.5169***	0.4651	5.8346***	3.0955***	17
H_0: GDP per capita growth does not Granger-cause population growth					
Statistic	8.8681***	6.6236***	4.9418***	2.0667**	17

Source: own elaboration based on Penn Tables. *Note:* the number of lags arises from the optimization of the Akaike Information criterion (AIC).

tries in Clusters 2 (*young economies*) and 3 (*transition economies*) have clear incentives to do so. This suggests that countries in Cluster 1 may be experiencing an aging and declining population, while those in Clusters 2 and 3 experience accelerated population growth. This pattern aligns with global migratory flows: countries in Cluster 1 (high-income) exhibit reduced or even negative natural growth and receive constant migratory flows from countries in Clusters 2 and 3, where natural growth is higher.

Impulse Response Analysis

Following the confirmation of a bidirectional causal relationship between population growth and GDP per capita growth, we investigated the nature of that causality using impulse-response functions. Figure 6 demonstrates that the series considered in the panel VAR model satisfy the stability condition (i.e., stationarity), as the eigenvalues fall within the unit circle.

Figure 6. Stability condition for panel VAR. *Source:* own elaboration based on Penn Tables. *Note:* all the eigenvalues lie inside the unit circle; the panel VAR model satisfies stability condition.

The first row of Figure 7 illustrates the initial scenario for the entire panel, indicating that a shock in one variable (impulse) leads to an increase (response) in the other. This suggests a positive association between both variables – higher population growth is associated with higher GDP growth, and vice versa. However, this observed increase dissipates after a few periods and may even be statistically insignificant in some cases.

In *mature economies*, where higher population growth does not directly result in increased GDP growth, a positive shock in economic growth leads to a positive impact on population increase, but the effect dissipates after 6 to 8 years. In the case of *young economies*, the outcome remains consistent: there is a positive response in population growth when economic growth increases. However, the response to an increase in population is a decrease in GDP per capita (although this effect is not significant).

For the *transition economies* cluster, the results align with the full panel analysis: higher population growth is associated with higher GDP growth, and vice versa.

Our findings highlight significant qualitative disparities in the dynamics of population and economic growth across the clusters. In the first cluster, a positive causal link exists between GDP and population, while in the other two clusters, the causal relationship is bi-directional but exhibits distinct signs.

As a final robustness check, we demonstrate that the series in levels (population and GDP) exhibit a long-term relationship, indicating cointegration, even when they are not stationary. Table 3 presents the findings, revealing a long-term relationship between population and GDP for clusters 1, 2, and 3. This result remains robust across different panel cointegration testing methods, including Kao, Pedroni, and Westerlund.

Figure 7. Impulse-responses for 2 lags VAR of population growth and GDP growth. *Source:* own elaboration based on Penn Tables. *Note:* each row, from top to bottom, corresponds to the full panel, Cluster 1 (*mature economies*), Cluster 2 (*young economies*) and Cluster 3 (*transition economies*).

Table 3. Cointegration analysis for GDP and population

Cointegration test	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Cluster 3
Kao test	-18.8771 (0.0000)	-19.3471 (0.0000)	-13.3758 (0.0000)
Pedroni test	-25.3720 (0.0000)	-31.3365 (0.0000)	-25.1081 (0.0000)
Westerlund test (some panels)	-6.3911 (0.0000)	-6.1411 (0.0000)	-6.0542 (0.0000)
Westerlund test (all panels)	-5.5484 (0.0000)	-5.2154 (0.0000)	-4.9614 (0.0000)

Source: own elaboration based on Penn Tables. Note: the Bartlett kernel method was used, with 1 augmented lag. *P*-values are provided in parenthesis. H_0 : no cointegration. In Kao and Pedroni tests, the statistic is the Augmented Dickey-Fuller *t*.

Conclusion

The study of the relationship between economic and population growth has a longstanding history in economics. However, there is no theoretical consensus on the scope and channels through which population and economic growth influence each other. Empirical evidence has not resolved the controversy; rather, the large volume of studies addressing the subject has produced contradictory results. With no unanimous conclusion emerging from the literature, we adopted an approach in the initial stage to group countries that exhibited similar trajectories in economic and population growth during the analysis period. By employing clustering techniques and introducing the notion of regimes, we aimed to identify groups of countries that are internally homogeneous in terms of dynamic connections between demographic change and economic growth. Simultaneously, these groups are distinctly different from one another.

In the first exercise, we identified three groups: *mature*, *young*, and *transition economies*. In the second stage, we conducted a causality analysis for the entire sample and each of the identified clusters. For the complete sample, a bidirectional causal relationship emerged between population growth and GDP per capita growth. When examining individual clusters, the results remained consistent: once again, a bidirectional causality relationship was observed between population and GDP. An exception was found in Cluster 1 (*mature economies*), where higher population growth did not translate into higher GDP growth. The impulse response analysis revealed that a positive shock in one variable had a positive impact on the other in all cases, except in the cluster of *young economies*. In this cluster, an increase in the population growth rate negatively affected economic growth, suggesting a potential population poverty trap. Although the result was not statistically significant, it implies a causal relationship with a negative sign.

While drawing policy recommendations from a general analysis is inherently risky, our results offer specific insights for each case. In *mature economies*, our findings do not support the notion that slow population growth negatively affects economic growth, suggesting a need to reconsider policies aimed at addressing population decline. Similarly, in *transition economies*, where population growth serves as a stimulus for economic growth, policies

should not aim to limit population growth. Conversely, for *young economies*, the recommendation to control population growth appears appropriate.

Given the complexity of the relationship between population growth and economic growth, further analysis is imperative. In future research, we intend to deepen the study by incorporating other relevant variables, such as physical and human capital, savings rates, and institutional frameworks, among others.

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Appendix

Table A1. Country Codes

ARG	Argentina	GAB	Gabon	NAM	Namibia
AUS	Australia	GBR	United Kingdom	NER	Niger
AUT	Austria	GHA	Chana	NGA	Nigeria
BDI	Burundi	GIN	Guinea	NAC	Nicaragua
BEL	Belgium	GMB	Gambia	NLD	Netherlands
BEN	Benin	GNB	Guinea-Bissau	NOR	Norway
BFA	Burkina Faso	GNQ	Equatorial Guinea	NPL	Nepal
BGD	Bangladesh	GRC	Greece	NZL	New Zealand
BOL	Bolivia	GTM	Guatemala	PAK	Pakistan
BRA	Brazil	HKG	China, Hong Kong SAR	PAN	Panama
BRB	Barbados	HND	Honduras	PER	Peru
BWA	Botswana	HTI	Haiti	PHL	Philippines
CAF	Central African Republic	IDN	Indonesia	PRT	Portugal
CAN	Canada	IND	India	PRY	Paraguay
CHE	Switzerland	IRL	Ireland	ROU	Romania
CHL	Chile	IRN	Iran	RWA	Rwanda
CHN	China	ISL	Iceland	SEN	Senegal
CIV	Côte d'Ivoire	ISR	Israel	SGP	Singapore
CMR	Cameroon	ITA	Italy	SLV	El Salvador
COD	D.R. of the Congo	JAM	Jamaica	SWE	Sweden
COG	Congo	JOR	Jordan	SYC	Seychelles
COL	Colombia	JPN	Japan	SYR	Syrian Arab Republic
COM	Comoros	KEN	Kenya	TCD	Chad
CPV	Cabo Verde	KOR	Republic of Korea	TGO	Togo
CRI	Costa Rica	LKA	Sri Lanka	THA	Thailand
CYP	Cyprus	LSO	Lesotho	TTO	Trinidad and Tobago
DEU	Germany	LUX	Luxembourg	TUN	Tunisia
DNK	Denmark	MAR	Morocco	TUR	Turkey
DOM	Dominican Republic	MDG	Madagascar	TWN	Taiwan
DZA	Algeria	MEX	Mexico	TZA	Tanzania
ECU	Ecuador	MLI	Mali	UGA	Uganda
EGY	Egypt	MLT	Malta	URY	Uruguay
ESP	Spain	MOZ	Mosambique	USA	United States
ETH	Ethiopia	MRT	Mauritania	VEN	Venezuela
FIN	Finland	MUS	Mauritius	ZAF	South Africa
FJI	Fiji	MWI	Malawi	ZMB	Zambia
FRA	France	MYS	Malaysia	ZWE	Zimbabwe

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